

Cancel Culture: Unveiling the Dark Side of Social Media for Brands – A Systematic Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The phenomenon and terminology of cancel culture are proliferating with the increasing use of social media in Indonesia. Through these platforms, the cancel culture movement is widespread and poses a significant threat to brands and products. However, research related to cancel culture in marketing is still limited. This research aims to describe the cancel culture phenomenon in marketing through a systematic literature review of 53 articles published from 2014 to 2024, with sources from ABDC and Scopus-indexed journals (Q1-Q4). The research identified relevant themes, methodologies, theories, variables, antecedents, consequences, and existing research gaps through this analysis. Based on these findings, the research proposes an integrative framework that describes the influence of cancel culture on brands, particularly the role of social media. The results also identify future research directions, including knowledge gaps in theory, methodology, and research context. The implications of this research are expected to contribute to developing marketing theory and practice related to cancel culture.

KEYWORDS: Cancel Culture, Consumer Behavior, Psychological Factors, Persuasion, Social Media.

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly connected digital age, social media has become a highly influential communication tool for individuals and companies. One of the phenomena that has emerged along with the development of social media is cancel culture, where a brand with a high reputation faces a firestorm that generates hatred towards the brand caused by ideological incompatibilities with high perceived importance, such as racism discrimination (Costa and Azevedo, 2024). According to Picarella (2024), for brands, cancel culture produces quite clear effects because it results in the withdrawal of any kind of support, including in terms of attendance, time, and money consumers have. Cancel culture is very similar to public condemnation that aims to enforce the rules of society. Actions can range from simply unfollowing to more active actions such as "boycotting," which seeks to refrain from buying a particular brand's products and persuade others to do the same.

Cancel culture is often driven by the presence of social media and has become a common phrase that refers to the practice of publicizing, shaming, and banning individuals or companies that are perceived to exhibit offensive, unethical, politically incorrect, or harmful behavior (Zembylas, 2023). This behavior is a continuation of a series of bolder social processes that emerged in the modern era and can be characterized as a form of expulsion that actively opposes compassion for others or companies by using social media as a form of offensive strategy without considering its potential impact (Jusay *et al.*, 2022). When these issues are raised on social media, consumer reactions can be swift and widespread, often resulting in product boycotts, discontinuation of support, or a significant drop in sales. The severe impact of this resentment goes beyond mere complaints and negative word of mouth, potentially destroying any brand and creating catastrophic consumer outrage (Abbasi *et al.*, 2023).

Existing literature suggests that cancel culture impacts public image and has significant implications for overall business performance (Abbasi *et al.*, 2023; Jusay *et al.*, 2022). Companies affected by cancel culture often face decreased customer loyalty, decreased market value, and internal problems such as loss of trust from employees (Abbasi *et al.*, 2023). This phenomenon shows that brands need to focus on product quality and be careful in taking a stance on sensitive social and ethical issues on social media. This is important to avoid cancel culture's potentially severe negative impact on business sustainability. A clear example of the cancel culture phenomenon can be seen in the case of Starbucks Indonesia in 2020 (Nugroho, 2021), Starbucks faced boycott calls in Indonesia in response to a global executive's statement supporting the LGBTQ+ community. Although the statement did not come from Starbucks branches in Indonesia, people who felt their values were threatened called for a boycott through the hashtag #BoycottStarbucks on social media. The campaign went viral among people who considered the company's views against local norms. This case shows that even if

statements are made overseas, local people's perceptions and attitudes towards global brands can still be affected, and sensitivity to social and cultural issues is crucial in maintaining positive relationships with consumers.

A similar case happened in Unilever Indonesia in 2021 (Sari, 2021), Unilever faced a boycott from Muslim consumers after it was perceived that its products did not support halal standards and were less responsive to their wishes. Although there is no exact sales data, the issue sparked widespread discussion on social media and several news platforms, demonstrating how cancel culture can generate significant reactions to brands in various markets.

Apart from social media such as Twitter, Facebook, or TikTok, other online platforms offer levers to change society and relate to cancel culture. One of the most popular sites is the Change.org website, which defines itself as "A social network for social justice" (May, 2012). Change.org is a website that allows users to create and sign petitions to advance various social causes by raising awareness and influencing decision-makers (Maxouris, 2020). One prominent example is a petition demanding the cancellation of the movie *Cuties* on Netflix (Morales Medina and Cabezas Clavijo, 2024). After the movie's trailer and poster were released, thousands of people protested by signing a petition on Change.org due to the alleged promotion of child sexuality. This public reaction triggered a mass outcry, which led Netflix to adjust promotional materials, but it still could not stop the boycott, which resulted in a drop in subscribers. This phenomenon shows that brands need to focus on product quality and be careful in addressing sensitive social and ethical issues on social media.

This research reviews critical gaps in the cancel culture literature and offers valuable guidance for future research, particularly regarding its impact on brands in the context of social media. This article has three main objectives: first, to identify influential recent research in the field of marketing published in ABDC and Scopus-indexed journals (Q1-Q4) in the period 2014 to 2024; second, to identify relevant vital themes, methods, theories, variables, antecedents, and consequences in the cancel culture literature on brands; and third, to uncover critical research gaps that can guide future academics. Based on the findings, this study proposes an integrative framework that includes research themes, key antecedents, independent variables, dependent variables, consequences, and mediators and moderators that play a role in the cancel culture and brand relationship.

METHODOLOGY

A review is considered a systematic review if it meets clear eligibility criteria, collects all relevant studies, and summarizes the results using reproducible methods to minimize bias and error (Brignardello-Petersen, Santesso and Guyatt, 2024). This process involves formulating appropriate research questions, identifying relevant studies through a comprehensive search strategy, and applying a structured methodology to reduce random errors (Yusuff, 2023). Systematic reviews can be classified into three types: (1) domain-based reviews, which focus on a specific subject; (2) theory-based reviews, which explore the theoretical framework underlying the research; and (3) methods-based reviews, which assess the research methodology used (Brough, 2019).

This study adopted a domain-based review approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of the relevant literature. The Scopus database was chosen as the primary source, given its comprehensive coverage among academic search engines and bibliographic databases (Gusenbauer, 2019). To identify relevant keywords, the initial search started with "cancel culture" and then analyzed the article titles to find the corresponding main keywords. The study's relevance was limited to academic articles, with the initial assessment process based on the title. If the title indicated a discussion of cancel culture in a brand or social media context, the complete reference was retrieved, including author, year, title, and abstract, for further evaluation.

From the initial search results, several main keywords were identified, including "Brand Boycott," "Online Boycott," "Social Media Backlash," "Brand Rejection," "Brand Cancellation," "Brand Hate," and "Cultural Boycott." Furthermore, this search combined these phrases using the BOOLEAN OR operator. The search formula included keyword combinations such as "Brand Boycott," "Online Boycott," "Social Media Backlash," "Brand Rejection," "Brand Cancellation," "Cultural Boycott," "Social Protest," OR "Brand Hate." The research covers academic journal articles published in English from 2014 to 2024 and excludes gray literature such as books, book chapters, trade publications, conference papers, editorials, news, and magazines. Only journals registered with the ABDC (Australian Business Deans Council) were considered in this study.

In addition, the scoping review used a systematic approach with independent double screening of titles and abstracts to eliminate irrelevant articles, ensuring that only appropriate studies were included in the review. This approach focuses on methods and tools to improve the efficiency of systematic review production (Affengruber *et al.*, 2024). This search identified 493 irrelevant articles (see Figure 1) out of 577 in Scopus. Duplicate articles were then eliminated, resulting in 122 kinds of literature. Further eligibility

criteria required articles to have a minimum of 10 citations, resulting in 86 articles after eliminating ineligible articles. Journals that were not relevant to the topic were then excluded, resulting in a final dataset of 53 articles. To organize the data, titles, authors, keywords, and database details were recorded in Microsoft Excel to avoid data duplication. Next, an in-depth critical review was conducted to extract each article's title, author, year, research objectives, methodology, theory, variables, findings, and future research directions. The extracted data were used for descriptive analysis and thematic analysis. Data visualization tools such as Tableau were used to represent the data more effectively.

Figure 1. PRISMA model
Source: (Kanaveedu and Kalapurackal, 2024)

RESULT

Descriptive analysis is an effective tool in data interpretation as it allows researchers to derive meaningful insights from the data collected (Selvamuthu, 2024). Data such as year of publication, social networking sites used, country where the research was conducted, type of industry, variables, and methods used were described descriptively to provide a more in-depth understanding of the literature reviewed.

YEAR OF PUBLICATION

The number of publications related to cancel culture increased from 2014 to 2024. In this study, 58 relevant publications were included. In contrast, others were excluded because they had less than ten citations, were in poor-quality journals, or were irrelevant to the subject area. A significant increase occurred in 2023; however, many articles from this year were not included due to low citation counts. The graph (Figure 2) shows that the highest number of publications occurred in 2021 and 2022, with 11 articles. This suggests that cancel culture is growing among academics, with attention increasing significantly in recent years.

Figure 2. Number of Publications per year

Source: Authors' Own Data

JOURNAL RANKING

Table 1 lists the journals, journal rank, and the number of articles corresponding to each journal included in this study. Most of the journals in this review are listed in ABDC with an A rating (56.6%), followed by A* (5.7%), B (26.4%), and C (11.3%) categories. The most significant contribution to the cancel culture literature comes from journals in marketing and human behavior. In addition, the journal rankings indexed on Scopus show that the majority of articles were published in Q1 (71.7%), followed by Q2 (26.4%) and Q3 (1.9%). The journals included in this study are interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary, reflecting the diverse approaches in cancel culture research from different fields of study.

Table 1. Journal Ranking and Number of Articles

Journal Rankings ABDC	Journal Name Q	Journal Name	Number of Articles	Contribution (%)
A	Q1	Journal of Business Research	9	16,98%
B	Q2	Journal of Islamic Marketing	4	7,55%
A	Q1	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	4	7,55%
B	Q1	British Food Journal	3	5,66%
A*	Q1	European Journal of Marketing	3	5,66%
A	Q1	International Journal of Consumer Studies	2	3,77%
A	Q1	Journal of Brand Management	2	3,77%
A	Q1	Journal of Consumer Marketing	2	3,77%
A	Q1	Journal of Strategic Marketing	2	3,77%
C	Q2	Social Science Journal	2	3,77%
B	Q2	Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC	2	3,77%
C	Q1	Strategic Change	2	3,77%
B	Q2	Asian Journal of Political Science	1	1,89%
A	Q2	B.E. Journal of Economic Analysis and Policy	1	1,89%

Journal Rankings ABDC	Journal Name Q	Journal Name	Number of Articles	Contribution (%)
A	Q1	Communication Research	1	1,89%
A	Q1	Current Issues in Tourism	1	1,89%
C	Q1	EuroMed Journal of Business	1	1,89%
A	Q2	International Journal of Market Research	1	1,89%
B	Q2	International Journal of Sports Marketing and Sponsorship	1	1,89%
B	Q1	International Review for the Sociology of Sport	1	1,89%
C	Q2	Journal of Asia Business Studies	1	1,89%
B	Q2	Journal of Business Strategy	1	1,89%
A	Q1	Journal of Consumer Affairs	1	1,89%
A	Q1	Journal of Consumer Behaviour	1	1,89%
A	Q1	Journal of Marketing Management	1	1,89%
A	Q1	Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly	1	1,89%
A	Q1	Public Relations Review	1	1,89%
B	Q3	Qualitative Market Research	1	1,89%

Source: Authors' Own Data

CITATION ANALYSIS

Google citations were used to identify each author's number of citations. Based on the data, Figure 3 presents the list of 10 authors with the most citations.

Figure 3. Quotation Analysis

Source: (Fetscherin, 2019); (Islam et al., 2019); (Bryson et al., 2021); (Abosag and Farah, 2014);(Dessart, Veloutsou and Morgan-Thomas, 2020); (Popp, Germelmann and Jung, 2016); (Zarantonello et al., 2018); (Kucuk, 2018); (Curina et al., 2020); (Mueller, 2021)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Most of the literature (89%, n = 47) focused on empirical research, while only 11% (n = 6) made theoretical contributions (see Figure 4). The majority of the literature used quantitative approaches (82%, n = 35), while 25% (n = 13) applied qualitative methods, and 9% (n = 5) combined both methods in a mixed approach.

Figure 4. Research Type and Approach

Source: Authors' Own Data

Table 2 shows that the majority of articles used a survey research design (57%, n = 30), followed by exploratory (26%, n = 14) and experimental (4%, n = 4) designs. Specific to experimental research designs, some researchers (n = 3; 6%) opted for a factorial design, as displayed in Table 3.

Table 2. Research design

No.	Research Design	Number of Articles	Contribution (%)
1	Experimental	4	8%
2	Exploratory	14	26%
3	Survey	30	57%
	Total	48	91%

Source: Authors' Own Data

Table 3. Types of Experimental Design

No.	Experimental Design Type	Number of Articles	Contribution (%)
1	Factorial Design	3	6%
2	Quasi-Experimental	1	2%
	Total	4	8%

Source: Authors' Own Data

SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Table 4 shows the sampling methods used in the previous studies. Most studies used non-probability sampling methods (79%, n = 42), while only 4% (n = 2) used probability methods. Convenience sampling was the most commonly used among the non-probability techniques, at 40% (n = 21). Meanwhile, Table 5 shows the sample audiences in the various articles, with consumers as the most widely used audience, accounting for 55% of 29 studies.

Table 4. Sampling Methods Used

No.	Sampling Method	Number of Articles	Contribution (%)
1	Convenience Sampling	21	40%
2	Purposive Sampling	15	28%
3	Quota sampling	4	8%
4	Snowball sampling	2	4%
5	Stratified Sampling	1	2%
6	Two-stage Area Sampling	1	2%
	Total	44	83%

Source: Authors' Own Data

Table 5. Sample of Audiences Researched

No	Metode Pengambilan Sampel	Number of Articles	Contribution (%)
1	Community Members	2	4%
2	Generation Y and Z	1	2%
3	Consumers	29	55%
4	Students	2	4%
5	Residents	5	9%
6	Social Media Users	5	9%
7	Tourists	1	2%
	Total	45	85%

Source: Authors' Own Data

VARIABLES

Table 6 shows the list of frequently used independent variables in the literature. The data clearly shows that the most used variables as independent variables are brand hate and subjective norms, each appearing 4 times (n = 4). In addition, Table 7 presents data on the dependent variables that are frequently studied. Based on the data, the most commonly studied dependent variable is brand hate, which appears in 13 studies (n = 13).

Table 6. Frequently used Independent Variables

No.	Frequently used independent variables	Number of Articles
1	Brand hate	4
2	Subjective norms	4
3	Brand rejection	3
4	Consumer animosity	3
5	Ideological incompatibility	3
6	Negative stereotypes	2
7	Market stature	2
8	Animosity	2
9	Product/service failures	2
10	Symbolic identity	2
	Total	27

Source: Authors' Own Data

Table 7. Frequently used Dependent Variables

No.	Frequently used independent variables	Number of Articles
1	Brand hate	13
2	Brand avoidance	3
3	Brand retaliation	3
4	Boycott intention	2
5	Customer boycott behaviour	2
6	Willingness to Boycott	2
	Total	25

Source: Authors' Own Data

SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES USED

Most studies in the literature used the Facebook platform (n = 5) as the object of study (see Figure 5). This is due to Facebook's ability to accelerate the spread of negative opinions through its commenting, group, and sharing features and broad user base, which is relevant for studying the cancel culture phenomenon. Only a few articles examined other platforms, such as YouTube (n = 2), blogs and websites (n = 2), Twitter (n = 2), Weibo and WeChat (n = 1), website and social media pages (n = 1), Twitter and Instagram (n = 1), and the combination of Line, Facebook and WhatsApp (n = 1).

Figure 5. Social Networking Sites

Source: Authors' Own Data

REGIONAL COVERAGE

The data graph shows that most of the studies were conducted in the United States (n=10), followed by the United Kingdom (n=5). The remaining four studies were conducted in countries such as South Korea, Pakistan, and France (see Figure 6). Three studies were conducted in Spain and India, while two studies were recorded in Saudi Arabia, Italy, Malaysia, Egypt, and Tunisia.

Figure 6. Area Coverage

Source: Authors' Own Data

THEORIES STUDIED

Table 8 shows that most of the literature is based on theories such as the Theory of Planned Behavior, followed by Consumer Animosity Theory, Consumer-Brand Relationship Theory, Equity Theory, and Social Identity Theory.

Table 8. Theories

Theory	Authors
Theory of Planned Behavior	(Delistavrou, 2022), (Sharma, Jain and Gupta, 2022), (Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2020), (Zarantonello <i>et al.</i> , 2018), (Palacios-Florencio <i>et al.</i> , 2021), (Salma and Aji, 2023), (Dekhil, Jridi and Farhat, 2017), (Abdul-Talib and Mohd Adnan, 2017), (Noor, Mansoor and Rabbani, 2022), (Costa and Azevedo, 2024), (Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2022).
Consumer Animosity Theory	(Abosag and Farah, 2014), (Ali, 2021), (Salma and Aji, 2023), (Abdul-Talib and Mohd Adnan, 2017)
Consumer-Brand Relationship Theory	(Dessart, Veloutsou and Morgan-Thomas, 2020), (Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2021), (Hashim and Kasana, 2019), (Kucuk, 2018)
Equity Theory	(Yadav and Chakrabarti, 2022), (Sameeni <i>et al.</i> , 2024), (Fetscherin, 2019), (Attiq, Hasni and Zhang, 2023)
Social Identity Theory	(Popp, Germelmann and Jung, 2016), (Sailofsky, 2022), (Khalifa and Shukla, 2021), (Abdelwahab <i>et al.</i> , 2020),
Attachment-Aversion Model	(Bryson and Atwal, 2019), (Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2020), (Bryson <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Brand Hate Theory	(Banerjee and Goel, 2020), (Bryson and Atwal, 2019), (Kucuk, 2019), (Bryson <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Duplex Theory of Hate	(Aziz and Rahman, 2022), (Attiq, Hasni and Zhang, 2023), (Kucuk, 2018)
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Theory	(He, Kim and Gustafsson, 2021), (Kucuk, 2019)
Identity-Based Consumer Behavior	(Dalakas, Melancon and Szczytynski, 2023), (Geusens, Ouvrein and Remen, 2023)
Social Dilemma Theory	(Muhamad, Khamarudin and Fauzi, 2019), (Shin and Yoon, 2018)
Social Rejection Theory	(Hu <i>et al.</i> , 2018), (Khalifa and Shukla, 2017)
Sternberg's Triangular Theory of Hate Animosity Motive	(Fetscherin, 2019), (Atwal, Bryson and Kaiser, 2022)
Appraisal Theory of Emotions	(Cuadras-Morató and Raya, 2016)
Attachment Theory	(Haase, Wiedmann and Labenz, 2022)
Big Five Personality Model	(Saldanha, Mulye and Rahman, 2023)
Boycott Motivation Theory	(Sameeni <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
Brand Dilution Theory	(Ali, 2021)
Brand Hate in Marketing	(Khalifa and Shukla, 2021)
Brand Hate Lifecycle Theory	(Farhat and Chaney, 2021)
Brand Loyalty Theory	(Atwal, Bryson and Kaiser, 2022)
Brand Rejection Theory	(Dekhil, Jridi and Farhat, 2017)
Cognitive Appraisal Theory	(Faulkner, Truong and Romaniuk, 2015)
Cognitive Dissonance Theory	(Akrouit and Mrad, 2023)
Cognitive Motivational Relational Theory of Emotions	(Abdelwahab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Consumer Animosity and Affinity Model	(Noor, Mansoor and Rabbani, 2022)
Consumer Behavior in Political Markets	(Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
Consumer Culture Theory	(Banerjee and Goel, 2020)
Consumer Ethnocentrism Theory	(Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
	(Abosag and Farah, 2014)

Theory	Authors
Consumer-Brand Relationship Framework	(Kim, Kim and Nakami, 2022)
Corporate Social Irresponsibility (CSI) Theory	(He, Kim and Gustafsson, 2021)
Dialectical Tensions Theory	(Veil and Waymer, 2021)
Erasure Paradox	(Veil and Waymer, 2021)
Ethical Ideologies Theory	(Alyahya <i>et al.</i> , 2023)vv
Exit-Voice Theory	(Yadav and Chakrabarti, 2022)
Expectation Confirmation Model	(Kim, Kim and Nakami, 2022)
Expectation Confirmation Theory	(Roy <i>et al.</i> , 2022a)
Free Riding	(Cuadras-Morató and Raya, 2016)
General Aggression Model	(Sameeni <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
Image Repair Theory	(Costa and Azevedo, 2024)
Interdependence Theory	(Fetscherin, 2019)
Legitimacy Theory	(Hu <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Moral Foundations Theory	(Shim <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Ostracism Theory	(Khalifa and Shukla, 2017)
Political Brand Identity Theory	(Banerjee and Goel, 2020)
Political Consumerism Theory	(Dalakas, Melancon and Szczytynski, 2023)
Power Within Relationships Theory	(Saldanha, Mulye and Rahman, 2023)
Product/Service Failure (PSF) Theory	(Kucuk, 2018)
Psychological Contract Violation Theory	(Alyahya <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
Psychological Predictors of Social Behavior	(Mueller, 2021)
Psychology of Hate	(Farhat and Chaney, 2021)
Reputation Repair Strategies	(Costa and Azevedo, 2024)
Scandal Spillover Theory	(Kintu and Ben-Slimane, 2020)
self-congruity theory	(Islam <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
Self-Construal Theory	(Khalifa and Shukla, 2021)
Self-Enhancement Theory	(Sameeni <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
Psychological Contract Violation Theory	(Alyahya <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
Psychological Predictors of Social Behavior	(Mueller, 2021)
Psychology of Hate	(Farhat and Chaney, 2021)
Reputation Repair Strategies	(Costa and Azevedo, 2024)
Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) Framework	(Yadav and Chakrabarti, 2022)
Sympathy Motive	(Cuadras-Morató and Raya, 2016)
Theory of Brand Image and Loyalty	(Abosag and Farah, 2014)
Theory of Cognitive Decision-Making	(Faulkner, Truong and Romaniuk, 2015)
Theory of Hate	(Yadav and Chakrabarti, 2022)
Theory of Reasoned Action	(Palacios-Florencio <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Triangular Theory of Hate	(Yadav and Chakrabarti, 2022)
Two-Step Flow Theory	(Mueller, 2021)
Word-of-Mouth Theory	(Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Theory of Reasoned Action	(Palacios-Florencio <i>et al.</i> , 2021)

Source: Authors' Own Data

ANTECEDENTS AND CONSEQUENCES

Table 9 shows that antecedents and consequences are most commonly found in the consumer behavior factor theme (n = 13), followed by the psychological factor theme (n = 5).

Table 9. Antecedents and Consequences

Theme	Antecedents	Consequence	Effect	Author
Psychological Factors	Brand Hate	Actual Self, Ideal Self	+	(Islam <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
		Negative Brand Social Self-Expressiveness	+	(Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
		Negative Brand Experience, Negative Brand Personality	+	(Roy <i>et al.</i> , 2022a)
		Neuroticism, Perceived Price Unfairness, Poor Call Quality, Post-Purchase Service Failure	+	(Attiq, Hasni and Zhang, 2023)
		Negative past experience, symbolic incongruity, poor relationship quality, ideological incompatibility, rumor	+	(Hashim and Kasana, 2019)
Consumer Behavior	Customer Boycott Behaviour	Reactive Eco-Innovation	+	(Shim <i>et al.</i> , 2021), (Alyahya <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
		Proactive Eco-Innovation	-	
	Intention to Boycott	Intrinsic Religious Motivation	+	(Muhamad, Khamarudin and Fauzi, 2019)
		Boycott Intentions	Attitudes, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioral Control, Consumer Animosity	+
	Decision to Boycott	Perceived Efficacy, Subjective Norm	+	(Salma and Aji, 2023)
		Message Credibility, Perceived Effectiveness, Expected Overall Participation	+	(Shin and Yoon, 2018)
	Negative eWOM	Brand Attitude, Subjective Norms, Anthropomorphic Tendency	+	(Sharma, Jain and Gupta, 2022)
		Boycott, Sabotage	Brand Hate	+
	Purchase Readiness, Purchase Aversion	Consumer Animosity	+	(Ali, 2021)
		Boycott Behavior	General Legitimacy, Boycott Usefulness, Animosity	+
	Decision to Participate in a Boycott	Ethical Idealism	-	
		Religiosity	+	(Dekhil, Jridi and Farhat, 2017)
	Willingness to Boycott	Animosity, Subjective Norms, Product Judgment	+	(Abdul-Talib and Mohd Adnan, 2017)
Positive Anticipated Emotions, Negative Anticipated Emotions		-		
Brand Retaliation	Attitude toward Offensive Advertising	+	(Noor, Mansoor and Rabbani, 2022)	

Source: Authors' Own Data

THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Thematic analysis is an important component of a framework-based systematic review, which categorizes research contributions into themes such as theory integration, actors, context, representation and methodology. In addition, various themes have been found

in the cancel culture-related literature, which are presented in Table 10. The main themes identified include: (a) persuasion and consumer behavior, (b) social networks and consumer behavior, and (c) psychological factors and consumer behavior (see Figure 7).

Table 10: Research themes

Theme	Author	Weight (%)
Persuasion and Consumer Behavior	(Attiq, Hasni and Zhang, 2023), (Cuadras-Morató and Raya, 2016), (Abdelwahab <i>et al.</i> , 2020), (Noor, Mansoor and Rabbani, 2022), (Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2020), (Saldanha, Mulye and Rahman, 2023), (Dalakas, Melancon and Szczytynski, 2023), (Abdul-Talib and Mohd Adnan, 2017), (Shin and Yoon, 2018), (Dekhil, Jridi and Farhat, 2017), (Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2022), (Ali, 2021), (Shim <i>et al.</i> , 2021), (Palacios-Florencio <i>et al.</i> , 2021), (Muhamad, Khamarudin and Fauzi, 2019), (Abosag and Farah, 2014), (Delistavrou, 2022), (Salma and Aji, 2023)	34%
Social Media and Consumer Behavior	(Costa and Azevedo, 2024), (Mueller, 2021), (Bryson and Atwal, 2019), (Yadav and Chakrabarti, 2022), (Geusens, Ouvrein and Remen, 2023), (Dessart, Veloutsou and Morgan-Thomas, 2020), (Kintu and Ben-Slimane, 2020), (Veil and Waymer, 2021), (Kim, Kim and Nakami, 2022), (Kucuk, 2021), (Ali, 2021), (Atwal, Bryson and Kaiser, 2022), (Abosag and Farah, 2014), (He, Kim and Gustafsson, 2021)	26%
Psychology and Consumer Behavior	(Sameeni <i>et al.</i> , 2024), (Alyahya <i>et al.</i> , 2023), (Hashim and Kasana, 2019), (Bryson <i>et al.</i> , 2021), (Faulkner, Truong and Romaniuk, 2015), (Aziz and Rahman, 2022), (Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2020), (Haase, Wiedmann and Labenz, 2022), (Geusens, Ouvrein and Remen, 2023), (Roy <i>et al.</i> , 2022a), (Veil and Waymer, 2021), (Kucuk, 2018), (Kucuk, 2021), (Akrout and Mrad, 2023), (Banerjee and Goel, 2020), (Fetscherin, 2019), (Islam <i>et al.</i> , 2019), (Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(Zarantonello <i>et al.</i> , 2018), (Sharma, Jain and Gupta, 2022), (Khalifa and Shukla, 2021)	40%

Source: Authors' Own Data

Figure 7. Thematic Analysis

Source: Authors' Own Data

PSYCHOLOGY AND CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN THE CONTEXT OF CANCEL CULTURE

In the literature on cancel culture, one theme that has received increasing attention is how psychological factors affect consumer behavior. Several studies have documented the psychological effects of cancel culture using theoretical approaches such as the Theory of Planned Behavior and Consumer-Brand Relationship Theory. Theory of Planned Behavior, for example, provides insight into how consumers' intentions are formed and how their behavior is directed when responding to cancel culture, especially in

considering social norms, attitudes, and perceived behavioral control. On the other hand, Consumer-Brand Relationship Theory allows for a deeper exploration of the emotional bond between consumers and brands. This theory suggests that a robust consumer-brand relationship can influence consumers' reactions in the face of cancel culture pressure, both in brand protection and reduced emotional attachment. Luan *et al.* (2023) explain that these emotional dynamics between consumers and brands play an important role in determining whether consumers will remain loyal or distance themselves from affected brands. Articles grounded in these theories not only reveal the negative side of cancel culture on consumer loyalty-such as loss of trust and reluctance to interact with brands-but also show the potential for understanding the positive aspects of consumer-brand relationships that survive social pressure. Research-based on Consumer-Brand Relationship Theory highlights that solid emotional ties can be protective, allowing some brands to survive even in the face of intense cancel culture waves.

CHARACTERISTICS OF CANCEL CULTURE

Most of this research explores the role of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) in understanding consumers' intention to cancel their support for a brand. TPB, introduced by Ajzen (1991), has become a popular theoretical framework for understanding consumer behavioral intentions across contexts. TPB includes three main components: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, all contributing to forming consumer intentions. In cancel culture, TPB becomes essential for understanding how consumers stop supporting brands involved in controversies, especially those related to social injustice, the environment, or ideological differences with consumers' values (Ajzen, 1991).

First, attitudes toward brand hate greatly influence participation in cancel culture. Brand hate often arises from consumers' negative experiences or perceptions of a brand, which can then encourage them to engage in negative electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM). Sharma *et al.*, (2022) showed that brand hate increases consumers' intention to share negative eWOM, further exacerbating the impact of cancel culture. In addition, ideological or symbolic incongruence between brands and consumers, such as in environmental issues or social values, is a significant trigger for brand hate and boycotts, especially when consumers perceive the brand as conflicting with their values (Costa and Azevedo, 2024; Hegner, Fetscherin and van Delzen, 2017; Fetscherin, 2019).

Second, subjective norms play a significant role in driving cancel culture. Subjective norms refer to social influences or pressure from significant others that make consumers feel compelled to participate in canceling support. Social media reinforces these norms by creating collective pressure, with younger generations, such as Gen Z and millennials, often motivated to express their disapproval publicly. Noor *et al.* (2022) show that solid social norms among certain consumer groups can drive engagement in cancel culture, especially in situations that trigger ideological controversy (Noor, Mansoor and Rabbani, 2022; Costa and Azevedo, 2024).

Third, consumers' perceived behavioral control is vital in shaping their intention to engage in cancel culture. Consumers who feel they have control or influence in expressing dissatisfaction with a brand tend to be more active in this behavior. Costa and Azevedo (2024) found that perceived social power through social media allows consumers to feel more empowered in spreading negative sentiment and supporting brand boycotts. Similar studies have also shown that this sense of control is essential in forming brand hate, leading to boycotts or counter-actions (Kim, Kim and Nakami, 2022; Abdul-Talib and Mohd Adnan, 2017). Cancel culture significantly impacts brands, especially consumer image and loyalty. Sarkar *et al.*, (2020) showed that the shame caused by a particular brand's actions or statements can encourage consumers to avoid the brand in the public domain, even though they may still use it privately. When cancel culture is fueled by ideological controversies, such as racism or religion, it can encourage boycotts and counter-action behaviors that significantly impact brand value (Salma and Aji, 2023). Several studies have also shown that brands that make public apologies or take corrective action can reduce the intensity of cancel culture. However, these efforts often require significant steps to restore consumer trust (Dekhil, Jridi and Farhat, 2017).

BRAND HATE

Strong negative emotions from consumers are one of the main factors that trigger cancel culture on social media. Consumers who feel hatred towards a brand often express their dissatisfaction through social media platforms, which ultimately influences the opinions of other consumers and creates a domino effect in the form of mass rejection or boycott of the brand. Based on several studies, there are several links between brand hate and cancel culture. First, negative experiences with brands are one of the primary triggers of brand hate. Consumers who feel disappointed due to dissatisfaction with product quality, poor service, or unethical

behavior from a brand tend to voice their disappointment on social media. For example, a study by Hegner, Fetscherin and van Delzen, (2017) showed that bad experiences experienced by consumers significantly increased the intensity of brand hate, which ultimately encouraged consumers to boycott or spread negative comments. Second, social self-expression is essential in increasing brand hate on social media. Consumers often avoid brands that are considered inconsistent with their social image or can cause shame when associated with the brand.

For example, a study by Sarkar *et al.* (2020) showed that negative perceptions of a brand's social image can cause brand hate through the shame or discomfort consumers feel. This then encourages them to express hatred towards the brand on social media. Third, brand personality and failure to meet consumer expectations are essential triggers in forming brand hate. Brands that fail to meet expectations or behave inconsistently with the values expected by consumers, especially regarding social responsibility or honesty, tend to receive intense hate reactions. Roy *et al.* (2022) noted that negative brand personality and failure to maintain quality or integrity directly contribute to increased brand hate and trigger boycott actions. Finally, social media's influence in expanding the reach of cancel culture towards brands is very significant. Social media facilitates the rapid spread of negative emotions and consumer complaints, so angry or disappointed consumers can easily share their negative experiences and influence other consumers' perceptions. According to Curina *et al.* (2020) brand hate expressed through social media significantly increases consumers' desire not to repurchase the product. It even triggers retaliatory actions, such as negative online comments or collective boycotts. Through these perspectives, it is clear that brand hate, as a negative emotion toward a brand, is vital in driving cancel culture on social media. Brands that fail to meet consumer expectations or have a negative social image are at high risk of being affected by cancel culture, especially with social media platforms that accelerate the spread of consumer dissatisfaction.

SOCIAL MEDIA AND CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

Another key theme emerging from the literature is the role of social media in influencing consumer perceptions of brands through social media. Cancel culture has become a phenomenon where people use social media platforms to "cancel" or withdraw support from a brand due to value inconsistencies or involvement in scandals perceived by the public as unfavorable. Ideological inconsistencies such as racial issues, LGBTQIA+ rights, and environmental issues are often the primary triggers, leading to criticism of brands through social media (Costa and Azevedo, 2024). For example, a study by Kintu and Ben-Slimane (2020) showed that when a brand is associated with a social media influencer involved in a scandal, such as Olivia Jade in the "Operation Varsity Blues" scandal, the brand is vulnerable to negative public perception impacts related to guilt by association. This emphasizes how cancel culture works through the social stigma attached to the brand's association with the influencer's behavior and the public's rapid response to events publicized on social media. Furthermore, in the context of anti-brand communities, Popp *et al.* (2016) suggest that platforms such as Facebook facilitate anti-brand communities that encourage collective engagement in criticizing brands. These communities use online interactions to amplify negative brand meanings and invite more users to join the anti-brand narrative. Another study by Salma and Aji (2023) on brand boycotts among Indonesian Muslims suggests that social norms and peer pressure can trigger consumer engagement in brand boycotts based on value inconsistencies, especially on religious and social issues. This consumer reaction is further strengthened through the use of social media as a means to voice disapproval of brands that are considered to violate religious values. In addition, research by He *et al.* (2021) on the #StopHateForProfit campaign against Facebook illustrates how consumers often consider companies committing social violations if they do not address hate speech on their platforms. This has led to massive boycotts from advertisers as a form of demand for corporate social responsibility (CSR). This study highlights how consumers today expect brands to be economically, socially, and ethically responsible. According to a study conducted by Dalakas *et al.* (2023), in some cases, consumers engage in "political consumerism" by rejecting or supporting brands based on perceived political affiliation. This process, often voiced on social media, encourages consumers to determine whether they will help or boycott a brand to reflect their political identity. Thus, cancel culture on social media not only shows the influence of consumers on the sustainability of a brand but also highlights how consumers' social and political values are a determining factor in the decision to boycott a brand. This perspective is supported by research showing that negative emotions such as brand hatred can trigger boycotts and extend retaliation against brands deemed inconsistent with consumers' values (Atwal, Bryson and Kaiser, 2022).

FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

This systematic review provides a comprehensive overview of how cancel culture on social media impacts brands and consumer behavior. It also identifies several important areas for further research, including the factors that trigger cancel culture, the role of online communities in amplifying or mitigating its impact, effective crisis strategies in responding to cancel culture, the long-term effects on brand loyalty, and the social and political dimensions of the phenomenon. Further investigation in these areas is expected to provide brands with deeper insights into the challenges and complexities of cancel culture in the digital era.

THEORY

This study reveals a gap in studies based on various theories related to cancel culture, brand backlash, and consumer behavior on social media. Some of the main relevant theories include the Theory of Planned Behavior, Consumer Animosity Theory, and Consumer-Brand Relationship Theory, each focusing on how consumers respond to brands based on their social and moral perceptions. The Theory of Planned Behavior (Delistavrou, 2022; Sharma et al., 2022; Sarkar et al., 2020) is often used to understand how consumers' intentions to support or boycott a brand are influenced by social norms, perceptual control and their attitudes toward cancel culture. On the other hand, the Consumer Animosity Theory ((Abosag & Farah, 2014; Ali, 2021) plays a significant role in explaining consumers' motivations to adopt negative attitudes toward brands involved in social or ethical controversies. In addition, Consumer-Brand Relationship Theory (Dessart et al., 2020; Curina et al., 2021) highlights the importance of emotional connections between consumers and brands and how these attachments can change due to the influence of cancel culture. Equity Theory and Social Identity Theory also offer valuable perspectives on how consumers' perceived unfairness or social group identity can influence their reactions to cancel culture directed at brands. Other theories, such as the Attachment-Aversion Model, Brand Hate Theory, and Duplex Theory of Hat, are relevant to exploring consumers' more intense emotional reactions to brands affected by cancel culture. These theories help us understand how feelings of hatred and rejection towards brands can arise due to consumers' moral or ethical views. Research also shows that the impact of cancel culture can vary across countries based on social media platforms, types of products or services, and cultural contexts. Therefore, an in-depth study that combines these theories is needed to understand the effects of cancel culture in various social and cultural contexts and enrich insights into consumer responses in an increasingly complex digital landscape.

VARIABLES

Research on cancel culture on brands still shows limitations in the literature related to variables such as brand type, product category, and social media platforms involved. The reviewed literature indicates a lack of research that explores the differences in the impact of cancel culture between large and small or local brands, as well as the influence of cancel culture on various product categories, such as fashion, technology, and food. In addition, there is a lack of studies explicitly discussing cancel culture on various social media platforms, such as Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok, which are often the main arenas for this phenomenon. Therefore, further research is needed to explore the impact of cancel culture on brands on various social media platforms. Further research is also needed to understand the characteristics of consumers who support cancel culture, including their motivations, emotional intensity, and moral perceptions of the brands it affects. In addition, socio-demographic characteristics such as age, ethnicity, cultural values, and gender must be considered in future research to understand how cancel culture is perceived and practiced by various consumer groups. Since cancel culture involves vital emotional aspects and moral values, future studies should also include variables such as consumer trust, brand loyalty, and attitude toward the brand in response to cancel culture. This will provide deeper insight into the long-term impact of cancel culture on the relationship between consumers and brands and how it affects consumers' intentions to support or boycott the brand.

MEDIATORS AND MODERATORS

Future research can explore negative experiences and unfulfilled expectations as mediators in the cancel culture phenomenon on social media (Islam *et al.*, 2019). Other consumer sentiment and public pressure dimensions also need to be studied as mediators in consumer responses to brands that are involved in controversial issues. Mediators such as Brand Hate, Brand Embarrassment, and Attitude Towards Boycott can provide additional insights into the emotional impact of cancel culture on brand perceptions.

Likewise, psychological contract Violations and environmental concerns deserve further study as mediators influencing consumers' decisions to support or reject brands amidst cancel culture (see Table 11).

From the literature reviewed (see Table 12), it is clear that research related to moderators is still limited and rarely studied repeatedly. Moderators such as affiliation with anti-brand communities, tendency to seek social approval, and self-improvement motivation are also essential in future studies (Costa and Azevedo, 2024). This research can reveal how these factors influence the intensity of cancel culture towards brands on social media, which can help brands develop more effective and adaptive response strategies to changes in public sentiment.

Table 11. Mediators used

Independent Variable	Mediator	Dependent Variable	Effect	Author
Unmet political expectations Symbolic incongruity Ideological incompatibility Political identity	Political Product Involvement	Brand hate	+	(Banerjee and Goel, 2020)
Intrinsic Religious Motivation	Subjective Norms Attitude Towards Boycott Self-Enhancement Make a Difference	Intention to Boycott	+	(Muhamad, Khamarudin and Fauzi, 2019)
Actual Self Ideal Self	Symbolic Incongruity Functional Incongruity	Brand Hate	+	(Islam <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
Reactive Eco-Innovation Proactive Eco-Innovation	Psychological Contract Violation Environmental Concern	Customer Boycott Behaviour	+	(Shim <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Negative Brand Relationship 1. Negative Emotional Connection 2. Two-Way Communication	Social Approval Oppositional Loyalty	Anti-Brand Community Participation	+	(Dessart, Veloutsou and Morgan-Thomas, 2020)
Message Credibility Perceived Effectiveness Expected Overall Participation	Likelihood of Success Possibility of Change	Decision to Boycott	+	(Shin and Yoon, 2018)
Anti-brand community participation	Oppositional brand loyalty Schadenfreude Re-interpretation of brand meaning	Brand effect on sports teams	+	(Popp, Germelmann and Jung, 2016)
Negative brand social self-expressiveness Brand hate Brand rejection Luxury brand rejection Consumer animosity	Brand embarrassment NeWOM intensity Perceived brand status Negative affect Boycott participation boycott motivation product judgment	Brand hate Consumer boycott Brand preference Brand dilution Purchase readiness purchase aversion	+	(Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2020) (Sameeni <i>et al.</i> , 2024) (Hu <i>et al.</i> , 2018) (Khalifa and Shukla, 2021) (Ali, 2021)
Attitude toward offensive advertising Consumer animosity	Brand hate Boycott attitude boycott intention	Brand retaliation Purchase amount	+	(Noor, Mansoor and Rabbani, 2022) (Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
Reactive eco-innovation	Psychological contract violation	Customer boycott behaviour	+	(Alyahya <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
Proactive eco-innovation Brand hate	Environmental concern Online complaining Offline negative word-of-mouth (NWOM)	Non-repurchase intention	-	(Curina <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Regional ethnocentrism	Brand identification brand trust brand love	Willingness to boycott	+	(Abdelwahab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)

Source: The Authors

Table 12. Moderation used

Variabel Independen	Moderasi	Variabel Dependen	Efek	Penulis
Reactive eco-innovation	Ethical Ideology	Customer boycott behaviour	-	(Alyahya <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
	1. Idealism		-	
	2. Realitivsm		+	
Attitudes	Socio-Political Control	Boycott Intentions	+	(Delistavrou, 2022)
Subjective Norms	1. Leadership Competence			
Perceived Behavioral	2. Policy Control			
	Demografis			
	1. Gender			
	2. Age			
	3. Education			
	4. Income			
Brand Attitude	Perceived Social Media Power	Negative eWOM	+	(Sharma, Jain and Gupta, 2022)
Subjective Norms				
Anthropomorphic				
Tendency				
Negative Brand Social	Consumer Susceptibility to Social	Brand Hate	+	(Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Self-Expressiveness	Influence			
	Brand Inner Self-Expressiveness		-	
Brand Hate	Big Five Personality Traits	NeWOM Intensity		(Sameeni <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
	1. Extraversion		+	
	2. Conscientiousness		+	
	3. Neuroticism		+	
	4. Agreeableness		-	
	5. Openness to Experience		-	
Brand Rejection	Self-Brand Connection	Brand Dilution	+	(Khalifa and Shukla, 2021)
	Self-Construal			
	Rejection Source			
Brand Rejection	Brand Identification	Need for Belonging and Negative Affect	+	(Khalifa and Shukla, 2017)
	Source of Rejection	Brand Evaluation		
Boycott Attitude	General Legitimacy	Boycott Behavior	+	(Palacios-Florencio <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
	Specific Legitimacy			
	Ethical Idealism		-	
	Social Influence			
	Brand Importance			
Consumer Animosity	Brand Judgment	Boycott Intention	+	(Salma and Aji, 2023)
	Counterargument			
Religiosity	Brand Loyalty	Boycott Decision	+	(Dekhil, Jridi and Farhat, 2017)
Attitude Toward Offensive	Religiosity	Brand Retaliation	+	(Noor, Mansoor and Rabbani, 2022)
Advertising				
Brand Strength	Online Purchasability	Actual Purchase Behavior	+	(Kim, Kim and Nakami, 2022)
Consumer Animosity	Geographical Area	Purchase Amount	+	(Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
Individualizing	Consumer Affinity	Boycott Intentions	+	(Shim <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Foundations	Moral			
Foundations	Crisis Attribution			
Binding	Moral	Anger (as Moral Outrage)		
Foundations				
Blame Attribution	Gender Identity	Cancel Involvement	+	(Mueller, 2021)
	Political Ideology			

Source: Authors' Own Data

Figure 8. Integrative Framework

Source: Authors' Own Data

ANTECEDENTS AND CONSEQUENCES

The literature explains that social media significantly influences cancel culture in a brand. Future research can focus on political affiliation and generational differences as variables influencing consumers' tendency to cancel a particular product or brand (Costa and Azevedo, 2024). In addition, research can also examine antecedents such as Consumer Perception of Brand and attachment style to clarify why consumers engage in cancel culture (Saldanha, Mulye and Rahman, 2023)

Focusing on these antecedents can help identify the main factors that trigger cancel culture and provide a deeper understanding of consumer motivations. Research also needs to examine the consequences of cancel culture, such as its long-term impact on brand

image, consumer loyalty, and repurchase intentions. This research will provide important insights for brands in anticipating and responding to cancel culture more effectively and help them understand how changes in consumer perception can impact brand sustainability and reputation.

PRODUCT CATEGORY SETTINGS

The lack of in-depth research across product categories suggests that findings on the impact of cancel culture on social media on brands are limited and cannot be generalized. Therefore, this study recommends that future research expand its scope to include product categories, particularly food and beverage brands across countries (Bryson and Atwal, 2019). In addition, future research could consider the impact of cancel culture in other communities, such as gaming, book, and technology communities, on social media platforms (Geusens, Ouvrein and Remen, 2023). Since cancel culture can impact each product category differently, it is essential to explore how different categories respond and adapt to the influence of cancel culture on social media. A more comprehensive study would provide a deeper understanding of the patterns of brand adaptation and resilience in the face of public pressure in an increasingly dynamic digital world. Thus, this research can help brands develop strategies tailored to their product categories and audience characteristics across social media platforms.

REGIONAL COVERAGE

Figure 7 shows that the contribution of various countries to the cancel culture marketing literature is still limited. Most of the existing studies focus on the United States (Shim *et al.*, 2021; Kintu and Ben-Slimane, 2020; Sailofsky, 2022; Hu *et al.*, 2018; Fetscherin, 2019; Alyahya *et al.*, 2023; Veil and Waymer, 2021; Dalakas, Melancon and Szczytynski, 2023; Mueller, 2021). Interestingly, the most significant social media users worldwide come from West Asia, followed by East Asia (We are Social, 2024). This suggests that an extensive research space exists in West Asia's emerging markets. More research is needed in mature and emerging markets, especially since the contribution from these countries is still minimal. Given that cancel culture is a developing area, especially in the context of social media and public discourse (Rahmawati and Dwiyantri, 2020), cultural differences between countries also influence the results of cancel culture. New findings can be generalized if more research is conducted in various countries. In addition, comparative studies of consumer behavior toward cancel culture in countries with similar geography and economy need to be studied in the future. This can provide a deeper understanding of the influence of culture, society, and economy on consumer responses to cancel culture in various contexts.

SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES

The study found that previous literature ignores platforms like TikTok, Snapchat, and Telegram. Therefore, future research needs to focus on these platforms to understand how their unique features—such as engaging short videos on TikTok, temporary content on Snapchat, and security and privacy on Telegram—influence user behavior and brand perceptions. This approach can provide a more comprehensive view of the dynamics of cancel culture on social media and the different platforms' specific roles in shaping consumer opinions and reactions to brands.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Most studies on cancel culture and its impact on brands in the dark side of social media have used quantitative approaches, indicating a lack of theoretical, qualitative, or mixed-methods approaches in the literature. In the future, studies on cancel culture should build on qualitative methods, such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, and case studies, to provide a deeper understanding of consumers' perspectives on the phenomenon, as these approaches can capture the complexity and multifaceted nature of cancel culture (Liu and Su, 2023). The use of mixed methods is also relatively limited, and more studies using this approach are needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of cancel culture on brand perceptions, as well as to understand its impact on collective action and validation through social media (Traversa, Tian and Wright, 2023).

Experimental studies on cancel culture have mainly used factorial designs, which limit further exploration of the various variables and interactions that may influence consumer perceptions and responses. In the future, more studies are needed with other experimental approaches, such as within-subject designs, to evaluate changes in consumer attitudes and behaviors in more depth

before and after cancel culture occurs (Welsh, Chatfield and Mainwaring, 2023). This approach can provide insight into the dynamics of consumer attitude change in a more realistic context.

In addition, most studies still use non-probability sampling techniques, which can affect the generalizability of the results. Therefore, future studies should consider probability sampling methods so that the findings represent a wider population (Khan, 2020). Future research must also involve more diverse samples, including generations X, Y, Z, and digital natives, to understand the variation in responses to cancel culture across generations.

In addition, studies on cancel culture tend to use a cross-sectional approach; to understand the long-term impact of cancel culture on brands and consumer behavior, longitudinal research is needed to track changes in consumer attitudes and perceptions of brands over time. This longitudinal approach is expected to provide in-depth insights into the ongoing effects of cancel culture on brand-consumer relationships.

LIMITATIONS

As with most studies, this study has several limitations. This article only uses the Scopus database and includes academic journals in the ABDC ranking (A*, A, B, and C) and journals indexed in Scopus Q1-Q4. In addition, the research data is focused on English-language articles published between 2014 and 2024. This study also does not include gray literature, such as books, book chapters, trade articles, conference proceedings, editorials, and other publications. These limitations may limit the diversity of sources and perspectives analyzed. Furthermore, some articles published closer to 2024 may have low citation counts, given the recent publication time and the limited number of citations that can be collected to date. These limitations are expected to be a concern for further research to expand the scope of sources and period to provide a more comprehensive insight into the cancel culture phenomenon and its influence on brands on social media.

IMPLICATIONS

This systematic review article aims to analyze the literature related to the role of cancel culture in influencing consumer attitudes and behaviors toward brands through social media. This study uses the Scopus database, focusing on journals listed in the ABDC ranking (A*, A, B, and C) and indexed in Scopus Q1-Q4 from 2014 to 2024. Four main objectives are formulated:

1. We are identifying the latest research on cancel culture.
2. We are identifying key research themes and variables.
3. We are identifying literature gaps.
4. Proposing an integrative framework to understand the relationship between cancel culture and consumer behavior towards brands.

First, this study found a significant increase in the number of publications related to cancel culture since 2019, especially in journals ranked B and A, which aligns with the increasing discussion of cancel culture on social media. The main themes in the literature include the influence of social media on brand perception, public opinion formation, and consumer switching behavior, with most studies focused on the United States and the Facebook platform, using quantitative methods with a cross-sectional research design. The Theory of Planned Behavior is frequently used, with antecedent variables such as brand hate and consequences in the form of subjective norms. This study also identified several gaps in the literature, such as the lack of coverage outside the United States, methodological variations, and exploration of less popular social media platforms, as well as the lack of research addressing cancel culture in the context of specific product categories and developing countries. Based on these findings, this article proposes an integrative framework that focuses on critical variables such as behavioral intentions, risk perceptions, and psychological factors, including themes, antecedents, independent and dependent variables, consequences, and mediators and moderators to understand cancel culture more comprehensively (see Figure 8).

For academics and practitioners, this study provides a comprehensive guide to the antecedents, consequences, mediators, moderators, independent and dependent variables, critical theories, and themes related to cancel culture and its impact on brands. This article also offers strategic insights for marketers and communication practitioners in dealing with cancel culture, emphasizing the importance of crisis management strategies and transparency in social media communications. Practitioners are advised to pay attention to consumer engagement, the impact of public opinion, and transparent disclosure of sponsorship, which, although risky

to trigger initial adverse reactions, can build long-term trust. In addition, marketers are expected to consider the social and cultural context of cancel culture and choose the most effective social media platforms to respond to the crisis wisely.

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